

COMBINED EFFECT OF COLD ROLLING AND HEAT TREATMENT ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF AL-TI ALLOY

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Abstract : This study investigated the combined effect of cold rolling and heat treatment on the mechanical properties of Al-Ti alloy. Samples of the alloy are cast in metal mould to obtain 0.94-2.19wt% mixes of titanium. These samples are grouped into untreated (as-cast) and those that are cold rolled to fifty percent reduction, homogenised at 5000C and soaked for one hour. The cold rolled and heat treated samples are normalised (RTn) and quench-tempered (RTq-t) at 1000C. All these samples are subjected to tensile, micro-hardness and microstructural evaluation. Results show remarkable improvement in the mechanical properties of the cold rolled and heat treated samples compared to the as-cast. In particular, the RTq-t samples containing titanium in the range of 1.7-2.2% demonstrates improve tensile strength by 24.7%, yield strength, 28%, elastic modulus, 38.3% and micro-hardness, 20.5%. The Al₃Ti phase being the most stable precipitate in the α -Al matrix appears to have been responsible for the significant improvement in the alloy's mechanical properties. It is concluded that quench and temper heat treatment is an effective method of improving the strength-strain ratio of cold rolled Al-1.7-2.2%Ti alloy.

Keywords : aluminum-titanium alloy, mechanical properties, precipitate, heat treatment

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